

Credible Deterrence without Reputation, Verification, or Disguise: A Blind, One-Shot Mechanism

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Abstract

Two strangers interact once; each can gain by exploiting the other, and no third party can observe who did what. Retaliation is costly, so under rational play its threat is empty – and repetition and reputation are unavailable. We study a blind, symmetric mechanism: both parties post an equal refundable stake; each holds a button that destroys the counterparty’s stake at a self-cost below it, the value burned, not transferred. The central result is an impossibility with an exact frontier: under blindness and anonymity no engineered instrument substitutes for genuine retaliatory disposition – a press not conditioned on the suffered harm falls on exploiter and cooperator alike and erodes deterrence – and instrumentation deters precisely up to the stake times the mass of the disposition at zero. Given credibility, deterrence reduces to $b > G/p$; self-selection at entry and a bounded exposure to externally motivated harm follow. The protective claim holds at a deterring fixed point whose existence we establish; its selection we state as open.

Keywords: deterrence; credible commitment; disposition; one-shot interaction; anonymity; costly punishment; self-selection; Trust Game.

JEL: D82, D86, K42, C72, C92.

1 Introduction

Klaus is looking for a used washing machine for 70 euros. He announces publicly: “I will buy for 70 euros, I do not care about the seller’s identity, and I will transfer the money first and then wait for the goods. My only condition: before the money moves, we both post a 150-euro deposit.” Attached to each deposit is a button: whoever presses it destroys the counterparty’s deposit and pays 40 euros in self-cost to do so; his own deposit is refunded. The public record attached to the mechanism tells any reader one number: at a self-cost of 40 euros, every second injured party presses. Gabi, a fraudster, accepts the deal, collects the 70 euros, and sends nothing. Klaus realizes the fraud and, in anger, presses the button.

At first glance the mechanism is thereby broken. Klaus is out the 70-euro purchase price and pays 40 euros in self-cost on top, so he stands at -110 ; Gabi has collected the 70 euros and lost her 150-euro deposit, and on net stands at -80 . Both are deep in the red, the victim deepest of all – and yet the mechanics do exactly what they should: the apparent pathology *is* the point. A threat that hurts and *never* compensates can only be deterrence, never insurance. For Gabi the episode is nothing personal: her aim is enrichment, she accepts Klaus’s harm rather than seeking it. She cannot tell whether a given Klaus belongs to the pressing half, so she computes with the public frequency: an expected haul of $70 - \frac{1}{2} \cdot 150 = -5$ – worse than an unprotected target elsewhere, the effort does not pay. An honest Stefan, who simply delivers,

by contrast never needs to fear the button. So Klaus and Stefan do business, Gabi seeks her victim elsewhere, and Klaus never learns that Gabi ever existed.

This story exposes an effect whose general form this paper investigates. Its setting is the bilateral commitment problem in its barest shape – the Trust Game (Berg et al., 1995), stripped of every institution that would dissolve it: two strangers interact, each can secure a private gain by harming the other, and no third party can observe or verify who did what. Four exclusions coincide – no repetition, no identity or reputation, no verifiable action, no arbiter – and they are no artifact but the real regime of one-shot exchanges between anonymous strangers, pseudonymous first contacts without a reputation store, and micro-interactions below any enforcement threshold. What unites these cases is that the exploiting action is not third-party verifiable – a broken informal understanding, a traceless informational asymmetry, withheld unobservable performance. Precisely there, repetition, reputation, and third-party enforcement fail at once, and precisely there the source of the threat’s credibility is no academic question.

We analyze a mechanism that resolves it without verification, identity, reputation, or compensation. Both parties post an equal, refundable stake b ; each holds a single button that *destroys* the counterparty’s stake at a self-cost $c < b$, with one’s own stake refunded and the destroyed value leaving the system entirely. Between the two parties, value never flows. We call this game form the *Nuke Mechanism*; it is an incentive rule, not an implementation (§3).

The construction is a *deterrence mechanism*, and it works precisely because retaliation is wasteful and never profitable – the washing-machine scenario in miniature: on the equilibrium path the exploiter is deterred and the catastrophe ($G - b < 0$) never occurs, while the off-path threat carries the on-path outcome. Two things follow, both made precise below: a *self-selection at entry* (the gain-motivated type does not even enter) and – the real difficulty – where the threat draws its *credibility* from at all in the one-shot, anonymous case.

Origin and Contribution. That costly punishment can sustain cooperation is the most robust result of the experimental public-goods literature – but always with *many* players, *repetition*, and *observable* contributions (Nikiforakis & Normann, 2008; Egas & Riedl, 2008; Sefton et al., 2007; Chaudhuri, 2011). From it we take two things: the *existence* of a self-costly retaliatory disposition and an *anchor* for its required effectiveness ($L \geq 3$). Our contribution is not the existence of the punishment but the *source of its credibility*: in a one-shot, anonymous encounter, repetition, reputation, and automation are foreclosed by construction (§2), and exactly *one* channel remains – the genuine, anticipated retaliatory *disposition* in Frank’s sense (Theorem 1). Behavioral economics supplies not the method – this is mechanism design (Maskin, 2008) – but the empirical warrant for the load-bearing assumption and the anchor for L . We borrow freely and say so: the deterrence criterion $b > G/p$ is shared with formal deterrence theory (Zagare & Kilgour, 2000), the *existence* of the vengeful type with Frank (1988), and the leverage $L = b/c$ is the cryptoeconomic *griefing factor* with its sign inverted (George, 2023; Leonardos et al., 2021). None of these is the contribution. What is new is an *erosion argument*: under blindness, any press that an engineered instrument – a device, a bounty, a mechanism-side rule – can produce is conditioned on events the exploiting action never touches; it therefore falls on exploiter and cooperator alike and, since a stake burns only once, cannot add to the deterrence margin – it preempts the disposition’s strike rather than compounding it (Theorem 1(b)). Only harm-contingent pressing deters, and the suffered harm is private to the victim, so only her genuine disposition can carry it. This is the step that separates our result from observable deterrence theory, where a visible Schelling commitment would already suffice: here, engineered instruments can *reprice* the disposition’s expression, but never substitute for it.

Contributions.

- (i) *Credible deterrence without reputation* (Prop. 2, Thm. 1): the central result is an *impossibility with a residue*. Under blindness and anonymity no engineered instrument *substitutes* for genuine retaliatory disposition: reputation needs identity, automation needs observation, and every device, subsidy, or bounty acts only through the effective self-cost of the harmed party’s own press (repricing, Thm. 1(c)), whether the money sits on the press or on the abstention – because any press *not* conditioned on the suffered harm falls equally on exploiter and cooperator and, a stake burning only once, preempts rather than compounds the disposition’s strike (erosion, Thm. 1(b)). This erosion result is the genuinely new step; in the *observable* games of deterrence theory a visible Schelling commitment would suffice – and even there only under perfect observability (Bagwell, 1995). Its constructive face is exact: instrumentation can deter precisely up to the frontier $b \Pr(\psi > 0)$, and no further (Cor. 2). The single surviving channel *reduces* the one-shot credibility problem of Berger & De Silva (2021) to a disposition documented in its *reality* and calibrated at a stationary fixed point – an existence check (Prop. 5), with selection the open problem (1).
- (ii) *The deterrence condition* (Lemma 2): given this credibility, exploitation becomes unprofitable once $b > G/p$ – the sole operative condition, thinned by the externally motivated mass to $(1 - m_\beta)pb > G$ (Cor. 1). The ratio $L = 1/\lambda$ names the effectiveness only *qualitatively* (small λ : anger is cheap to act on, the stake hits hard); its experimental threshold is a multi-player anchor whose bilateral magnitude is not established.
- (iii) *Self-selection at entry as a consequence* (Prop. 4): together with the outside option, deterrence produces a self-exclusion of the gain-motivated type – an adverse-selection unraveling with a displacement externality, not a standalone sorting result.
- (iv) *Invisible exclusion* (Rem. 4): because the gain-motivated type does not enter in advance, he disappears from the pool from which the protected party draws.
- (v) *Destruction as a no-profit condition* (Prop. 6): burning rather than transferring keeps pressing purely dispositional; “no value flows between players” is the clean form.
- (vi) *Bounded exposure instead of impossibility* (Prop. 7, §5): the only residual is the quantifiable exposure to externally motivated harm.

2 Related Work

The Bilateral Commitment Problem. The setup is the trust or investment game (Berg et al., 1995): a first mover who can be expropriated by a second mover. Classical resolutions invoke repetition and reputation (Kreps & Wilson, 1982; Milgrom & Roberts, 1982), self-enforcing relational contracts (Telser, 1980; Klein & Leffler, 1981), or third-party enforcement. Ours invokes none of these; it rests on a single round and on anticipated disposition.

Deterrence in the One-Shot Game. The credibility problem we address is the one named by Berger & De Silva (2021): deterrence rests on a threat of retaliation, but since retaliation is costly to the defender, in the one-shot game it is empty – an injured defender gains nothing from retaliating, so under rational play the threat is hollow. Berger & De Silva (2021) resolve this via *costly reputational information*; their result even sharpens it – dense information about past actions makes deterrence collapse, only minimal information sustains it, so reputation in dense form is counterproductive – which supports our doing without it. Closest to our construction is Calabuig et al. (2016): a Trust Game with costly punishment whose effect hinges on the *punishment capacity* – the share of the counterparty’s payoff the punisher can destroy, hence exactly our leverage L . Their setting is *observable* and with identity, and their question is the promotion of trust under rational play, not credibility from disposition; we adopt the capacity quantity and remove observability and identity. Notably, Calabuig et al. (2016) find their own

data only weakly consistent with deterrence, better explained by a *crowding-out* of intrinsic motivation; we state the adverse direction first. If a *visible* sanctioning capacity, backed by identity, already deters only weakly, one might a fortiori doubt a blind, anonymous variant. But crowding-out turns on *visibility* – an observable sanction institution displacing intrinsic motivation – and blindness removes precisely that institution: there is no visible sanctioning authority to crowd out the injured party’s own disposition. What survives in their data is the dispositional, not the rational-capacity, channel – the one our mechanism isolates. The reading is thus a qualification we adopt, not evidence we suppress.

Formal Deterrence Theory. The credibility of costly threats is the subject of game-theoretic deterrence theory, in particular *Perfect Deterrence Theory* (Zagare & Kilgour, 2000), whose prominent application is mutual deterrence (Mutually Assured Destruction). Its deterrence criterion is ours – a rational target is deterrable exactly when the action’s cost exceeds its expected benefit, here $b > G/p$ – and so is its resolution of credibility: it rests on types who actually *want* to carry out the threat (a credible player prefers conflict to capitulation), whose distribution the challenger knows under incomplete information. Our ψ is such a type. Three things distinguish our construction. *First, the setting:* Perfect Deterrence operates in *observable* games, whereas ours is blind and anonymous, so neither automation nor reputation is available as a credibility channel (Theorem 1) – precisely this exclusion is our subject. *Second, the origin of the type:* where Perfect Deterrence posits the retaliatory preference as given, we ground it empirically and take from the same literature the anchor for its effectiveness L . *Third, the character of the type:* where the “hard type” is permanently action-guiding, ψ is a latent capacity, fixed once drawn but harm-activated and non-persistent in its expression – developed under *Triggered Disposition* below.

Costly Punishment and the Emotions. Schelling (1960) showed that *credibility*, not capability, binds, and Frank (1988), building on Hirshleifer (1987), that the emotions – vengefulness above all – are evolved commitment devices that make otherwise incredible threats of costly retaliation believable. The experimental backbone is firm: that agents punish defectors at their own cost and thereby sustain cooperation is robust (Fehr & Gächter, 2002; Masclet et al., 2003), and the *effectiveness* of such punishment – the factor by which a sanction lowers the punished party’s income, our L – rises monotonically with contributions, with a rule-of-thumb threshold $L \geq 3$ below which punishment fails to halt the decay (Nikiforakis & Normann, 2008; Sefton et al., 2007; Chaudhuri, 2011; Egas & Riedl, 2008). This evidence is throughout from *multi-player, repeated, observable* games; we transfer the effective ratio into a *bilateral, one-shot, blind, anonymous* setting, with two qualifications stated openly: the threshold is context-dependent – an integrative study over 360 conditions finds welfare effects of punishment from -44% to $+43\%$ (Alsobay et al., 2026), so the 1:3 ratio is a rule of thumb, not a constant – and whether it transfers quantitatively to the bilateral, blind setting is *not shown*; we use it as a plausibility anchor, not a proof (Remark 1). Guala (2012) presses the external-validity objection against this laboratory corpus – spontaneous costly peer punishment is rare in the field; we take it as delimiting rather than refuting: the field rarely supplies a cheap, consequential retaliation channel, and building and pricing one is the mechanism’s contribution – whether the disposition expresses through it is the measurement question of Remark 1.

Second-Party Evidence and Illegibility. From this literature we take exactly one thing: the *existence* of the self-costly retaliatory disposition ψ , documented also in *one-shot, fully anonymous second-party* form – the costly rejection of unfair ultimatum offers (Güth et al., 1982) and, closer still in timing, the targeted bilateral sanctioning of defectors *after* the defection is sunk in one-shot cooperation games (Falk et al., 2005), where cooperators direct costly punishment almost exclusively at those who wronged them – as against the third-party or group

punishment of the public-goods games (Fehr & Fischbacher, 2004). That the destructive modality itself – paying to burn another’s money, unprovoked and under anonymity – is available to real populations is documented directly (Zizzo & Oswald, 2001; Abbink & Sadrieh, 2009); in §5 this anchors the residual, not the engine. The ultimatum rejection destroys the wrong before it is consummated; the Falk et al. (2005) sanction, like our press, strikes after the gain is irreversibly consumed – the setting-correct analogue on both counts, second-party *and* ex post. We take neither its *legibility* nor its *magnitude*. Contra Frank, whose emotions work because they are *legible* (a visible blush, manifest rage), our disposition is by construction illegible and carries the threat only through the *statistical anticipation* of its frequency $p(c)$ – credibility by expectation over a population, not by a signal read off an individual. And because only existence, not magnitude, is documented, the deterrence condition $b > G/p$ is a design requirement, not an empirical finding. Our own contribution is the cost structure (λ small, L large), making the disposition cheap to act out and devastating in effect. We deliberately do *not* invoke Williamson (1983): a hostage is a valuable object *exchanged* with the counterparty, whereas our stake is destroyed and handed to no one – self-binding by money-burning (Ben-Porath & Dekel, 1992), a forward-induction cousin, not a hostage.

Preferences as Commitment under Unobservability. Reading a genuine preference as a commitment device raises a question this paper cannot evade: can such a preference persist when no one observes it? The indirect evolutionary approach (Güth, 1995; Huck & Oechssler, 1999) endogenizes preferences by letting material success select among them, and its central negative result cuts against us: with *unobservable* preferences, stable outcomes must be Nash equilibria of the material game (Dekel et al., 2007; Ely & Yilankaya, 2001; Ok & Vega-Redondo, 2001) – and the press, materially $-c$, is no such action. Reciprocal preferences survive under perfect or almost-perfect observability (Sethi & Somanathan, 2001); and Friedman & Singh (2009), analyzing equilibrium vengeance directly, sharpen the point to our case: vengeful types survive in their hybrid equilibrium precisely because a noisy *signal* of type exists, while at zero legibility only the pooling equilibrium without vengeance remains. We answer with a scope separation rather than a counter-theorem. The mechanism does not claim that ψ is stable *within* the blind regime; it *imports* a disposition whose present existence is data, not theory (Assumption 1), and whose maintenance plausibly occurs *outside* the regime – in the observable, repeated interactions of ordinary life, Frank’s original habitat, where legibility and reputation reward the type. So long as blind, anonymous encounters are a small share of an agent’s interactions, the erosion pressure identified by this literature operates on a margin the mechanism does not occupy; the mechanism free-rides on a trait maintained elsewhere, as it free-rides on the ambient norm N . The price of this answer is stated openly: commitment stability is assumed as an empirical fact about present populations, not derived, and its long-run erosion – an agent who never comes to press shedding the disposition – is exactly the risk recorded as open problem (1) (§5), for which the preference-evolution results above supply the pessimistic benchmark.

Triggered Disposition. Crucially, ψ does not act as a permanently action-guiding type. What is drawn as a fixed trait and over which $p(c)$ integrates is the *latent capacity* for retaliation; the “crazy type” (Kreps & Wilson, 1982; Milgrom & Roberts, 1982), by contrast, is an exogenous, permanently action-effective property that a strategic player imitates over *repetition*. The capacity ψ stays inert until suffered injury activates it into a *transient state* in an otherwise normal agent, consumed in the act of retaliation. Because the state arises only through injury it is *self-addressing* – only the party actually harmed becomes ready to press – which is why the mechanism needs neither repetition nor the ability to identify the wrong. An agent irrational *independently* of injury is therefore not the engine ψ but the bounded residual of malice β (§5). Decisively, the mechanism need not read any *single* counterparty’s disposition: whether a given counterparty presses is indeterminate in advance, and exactly this indeterminacy keeps

the threat inescapable, since the exploiter cannot pick out a yielding counterparty. What carries the deterrence is the correct *population belief* $p(c)$, not the legibility of the individual; once a sufficiently disposed party has in fact been harmed, it presses reliably. Unpredictable in the trigger, determinate in the course – two distinct moments, not a contradiction.

Selection through Self-Exclusion. Who enters determines the pool’s quality. This is not Spence signaling (Spence, 1973) (no costly signal of the good type) but its dual – *self-exclusion of the bad type* via his outside option, closer to participation sorting and to the reverse-run adverse-selection unraveling of Akerlof (1970), not a menu screening (Rothschild & Stiglitz, 1976) that would require a principal with an option menu. The resulting positive assortment – cooperators more often meet cooperators – is familiar from biological markets and partner choice (Noë & Hammerstein, 1994), but there it arises through *choosing* (leaving a defector, searching for a better partner) and presupposes repetition or reputation; our mechanism produces the same assortment in *one* anonymous round through repulsion rather than choice. That raising an offense’s expected cost *displaces* offenders rather than eliminating them is the economics of crime (Becker, 1968); we treat this displacement as a cost (§5), not a benefit.

The Impossibility of Fair Exchange. For the guarantee space there is a closing result: *strong* fair exchange – both parties receive the counterparty’s performance or neither does – is impossible without a trusted third party; Pagnia & Gärtner (1999) prove this by reduction to the consensus problem. Our regime lies doubly outside that space: the action is not verifiable, so fairness of settlement is not even expressible as a protocol property – and the mechanism does not promise it. It replaces the impossible guarantee with deterrence; which credibility channel alone remains for that purpose under blindness and anonymity is Theorem 1.

Related Deposit Mechanisms. Structurally related is dual-deposit escrow (Zimbeck, 2014; Bigi et al., 2015; Asgaonkar & Krishnamachari, 2019), where both sides post bonds and the honest equilibrium is subgame-perfect – under *rational* play, with an *observable* outcome and *symmetric stalemate* burning. Ours differs on all three axes (disposition-based credibility, blindness, one-sided asymmetric pressing) and targets what those designs cannot reach: non-verifiable behavior without an arbiter. The contrast is sharpest at the default: in that family funds release only on *mutual* signature, so destruction – or an indefinite lock – is what happens when nothing happens, and each side holds a costless veto over settlement, leaving the frozen pot inside the bargaining set – an exposure the family has flagged as an extortion problem, and sought to mitigate, since its founding document (Zimbeck, 2014) –; in our game form settlement is the default and destruction a priced, unilateral act (cf. Remark 2), which removes the threat from the bargaining set altogether – burned value cannot be bargained over. Tabarrok (1998) is a further cousin – a refundable contribution returned if a threshold is not missed. We name the prior-art risk concretely: mutual destruction already appears elsewhere – in atomic-swap protocols, where it neutralizes bribery incentives (Tsabary et al., 2021), and, as a forfeitable bond against value destruction, in designs for the contestable control of decentralized organizations. Both operate under an observable outcome and rational play and know neither blindness nor the dispositional credibility channel; they delimit our construction without anticipating it. A mechanism with mutual destruction may nonetheless already be described in some form unknown to us, and our novelty claim is only as strong as the underlying search (§6).

Money Burning under Non-Verifiable Information. That *destruction* is the clean instrument where the trigger is private has a canonical ancestor in contract theory. When performance is evaluated subjectively – observed by one party, verifiable by none – optimal contracts burn surplus: in MacLeod (2003) bonus payments go to a third party rather than back to the principal, precisely because a transfer *between* the parties would corrupt the report that triggers it;

Fuchs (2007) shows that the optimal contract under repeated moral hazard with private evaluations *requires* burning resources; and in Levin (2003) relational pay under subjective measures is disciplined by destroying continuation surplus. The diagnosis is shared – where nothing is verifiable, transfers corrupt and only destruction keeps incentives clean; our no-profit condition $\alpha < \lambda$ (Prop. 6) is the same logic transposed – but the engine is not: there the burn is enforced by the continuation value of an ongoing principal–agent relationship and serves truthful *reporting*; here there is no report, no principal, and no continuation, and the burn is carried by the injured party’s genuine disposition in a single anonymous round. The ancestry delimits our construction on the *instrument*; the credibility source lies outside its reach.

The Griefing Factor. As a quantity, our ratio $L = b/c$ – victim loss per unit of attacker self-cost – is the *griefing factor* that cryptoeconomic mechanism design uses to gauge sabotage resistance (George, 2023; Leonardos et al., 2021). The use is inverted. There the designer *minimizes* it: a griever is a nuisance driven by *external* incentives, and a small factor makes sabotage not worthwhile (George, 2023) – exactly our externally motivated β -type (§5), which we bound as a residual. We *maximize* the same factor into a deterrence lever, made credible not by external incentives but by the injured party’s genuine, harm-triggered disposition – a channel absent from a literature concerned with robustness against indifferent saboteurs. Leonardos et al. (2021) analyze griefing factors in non-homogeneous populations under evolutionary stability; we share the population lens but invert the phenomenon’s sign – their griefing dissipates resources, ours sustains a credible threat.

3 The Mechanism

3.1 Environment

Two risk-neutral, symmetric players, i and j .¹ There is a single *exploitation opportunity*: one player (ex ante, by symmetry, either) can choose an action X that yields him a private gain $G > 0$ and inflicts a material harm $D > 0$ on the other, or the cooperative action C, which yields the normalized baseline. *The mechanism observes neither the opportunity nor the action.* There is no payment, delivery, or role distinction; “X” is any move that benefits the mover at the other’s expense. Both players post a stake because ex ante either can take the exploiter’s role; the symmetry of the stakes reflects this ex-ante indistinguishability, not an already-realized allocation of roles.

Each player has a private *retaliatory disposition* $\psi \geq 0$: the psychic benefit he would derive from destroying the counterparty’s stake after suffering harm – equivalently, the effective willingness to press at the node in his own interest, which the documented retaliatory emotions instantiate. Its intensity is not constant but scales with the magnitude of the suffered harm D and with the prevailing population norm N of what counts as a wrong, $\psi = \psi(D, N)$ – the experimental analogue being that the rejection of unfair offers rises with their unfairness (Güth et al., 1982) (a pre-consumption analogue; cf. the timing note in §2). The baseline analysis fixes (D, N) at their realized values and works with the induced press-readiness, so that D enters the press decision only through ψ ; the norm N is exogenous at the press node – a feature of the population, not the presser’s strategic belief about the counterparty – so the press decision remains belief-independent (§5). Dispositions are drawn from a population distribution; we write

$$p(c) := \Pr(\psi \geq c),$$

¹Risk neutrality and a deterministically realized ψ are load-bearing simplifications. Risk aversion makes $b > G/p$ conservative (a risk-averse exploiter is easier to deter); a ψ realized stochastically in the heat of the moment smooths the press threshold $\psi = c$ without changing the survival form of p .

the probability that a counterparty’s anger covers a press at self-cost c . By construction p is non-increasing, with $p(0) = 1$ and $p(c) \rightarrow 0$ as c grows. $p(c)$ distributes the *latent capacity* ψ – a fixed, drawn trait –, not its expression; whether this capacity expresses itself in an actual press is harm-contingent (Assumption 2). The belief in $p(c)$ is the *stationary aggregate* frequency of the population, learnable from the public record of presses; that a self-consistent such frequency exists is shown in Prop. 5, while its selection and the learning dynamics are deferred to open problem (1) (§5).

Assumption 1 (Reality of Disposition). Dispositions ψ are real: an injured player with activated capacity $\psi \geq c$ actually presses. This is empirically anchored – the documented altruistic punishment is exactly this behavior (Fehr & Gächter, 2002).

Assumption 2 (Activation by Wrongful Harm). The capacity ψ is activated solely by *wrongfully suffered harm* – harm that the prevailing norm N marks as a wrong done to the bearer. The paradigm case is suffered exploitation: a counterparty choosing X and the agent bearing D . The same clause covers the unprovoked destruction of one’s stake by an externally motivated press: under any norm in whose regime the mechanism protects, gratuitous destruction is a wrong, so its victim’s capacity activates – a consequence cashed in as the counterstrike bound on the β -residual (§5). What the clause *excludes* is norm-covered sanction: an exploiter whose stake is destroyed in answer to his own X has, under N , suffered no wrong, and his capacity stays inert. We state this norm-keying as a behavioral *posit*, not as an empirical inheritance, because the experimental record qualifies it: where counter-punishment is possible, roughly a quarter of punishments are retaliated, and the mere prospect of retaliation lowers punishers’ willingness to sanction (Nikiforakis, 2008); across societies, the punishment of cooperators itself varies widely (Herrmann et al., 2008) – both readable as *self-serving perception of the norm*, a sanctioned party construing his own sanction as a wrong, and a further caution against any universal calibration. The posit is therefore priced for failure rather than assumed away: a counterstrike probability $q > 0$ raises the victim’s effective self-cost from c to $c + qb$ and lowers p accordingly (§3) – exactly the depressing effect that Nikiforakis (2008) documents – and the deterrence condition retains its form $bp(c + qb) > G$. Crucially, the activation is a property of the agent’s *private disposition* responding to the ambient norm, not a classification the *mechanism* performs; the mechanism remains blind and adjudicates nothing (§5).

Assumption 3 (Calibration to the Stationary Frequency). A potential exploiter acts, before exploiting, on the *stationary aggregate* press frequency $p(c)$ of the population – learned from the public record of presses, not from any individual’s reputation. Unlike Assumption 1, the *level* of this frequency is not handed down empirically; it is a fixed point of the pool composition, shown to exist in Prop. 5. What remains open is not *whether* a self-consistent $p(c)$ exists but *which* fixed point is selected and whether aggregate experience converges to it (open problem (1), §5) – and exactly here, not in the reality of the disposition, sits the residual fragility on which credibility rests. One tension belongs in this assumption’s own text: $p(c)$ is a conditional frequency – presses per suffered harm – and on a well-deterred path numerator and denominator vanish together, so the public record thins exactly where the mechanism succeeds. Calibration must then feed on off-path events – the β -residual of §5, non-deterred high- G exploitation, entry churn – and on deliberate experimentation (Remark 1); the learning dynamic of open problem (1) must run on a signal that the mechanism’s own success attenuates.

What follows rests on Assumptions 1–3; load-bearing and documented is the reality of the disposition (Assumption 1), while the calibration (Assumption 3) is a stationary fixed point whose existence we establish (Prop. 5) and whose selection and dynamics remain open. Taken together, Assumptions 1–3 *define* the regime in which the mechanism functions as protection: a population in which the meaning of exploitation – what counts as the wrong that ψ responds to – is already settled and shared. Where it is not settled, the constitutive case applies (§5, §4.4).

Solution Concept. $M(b, c, \alpha)$ is a game of *incomplete information*: ψ is private, and an exploiter knows only the distribution $p(c)$. Perfect Bayesian equilibrium has no additional bite here because the *press decision is belief-independent* – its payoff ($\psi - c$, in general $\psi - c + \alpha b$, with $\psi = \psi(D, N)$ fixed by the realized harm and the exogenous prevailing norm) depends solely on one’s own type and the ambient norm, not on any belief about the counterparty – and because the exploiter, observing nothing beforehand, never updates. (This belief-independence is exact at the canonical $q = 0$; under $q > 0$ the press risks one’s own stake and a belief about the counter-disposition re-enters, which the retaliation tax $c + qb$ of §3 prices in reduced form.) The concept thus reduces to Bayes–Nash with sequential rationality at the press node: an injured type ψ presses exactly when $\psi \geq c$, and the exploitation decision is optimal given $p(c)$. Off-path beliefs are unrestricted but inconsequential, and the symmetric stake signals no type, so forward induction has no bite; the existence and conditional-uniqueness statement in §5 is meant in this sense. Direct pre-play talk, finally, is cheap and babbles: every type – disposed or not – gains from the counterparty believing p high, so all issue the same assurances and no message separates; the game form accordingly contains no message stage, and all conditioning-relevant talk is routed through the device formalism of Definition 2.

3.2 The Mechanism $M(b, c, \alpha)$

Fix a stake $b > 0$, self-cost c with $0 < c < b$, and a transfer share $\alpha \in [0, 1]$. An entity that can hold, refund, transfer, or irrevocably destroy posted funds executes the following *game form*. On this entity the mechanism places *one* credibility requirement: it must be *bound* to the announced destruction and may neither retain nor secretly redirect the forfeited stake – otherwise a self-interested executor deviates precisely from the defining action (burning) (Akbarpour & Li, 2020). Which entity provides this remains open, yet the candidates are not interchangeable: an automated contract enforces the binding mechanically, whereas a trustee or an institution must itself be bound to irreversibility – a commitment problem of its own. We thereby remove the trusted *judge* (the mechanism adjudicates nothing), not the bound *executor*. The posted stakes are irrevocably locked from Stage 1 through Stage 4; in particular, an exploiter cannot withdraw his stake after the action and before the press. Before Stage 1, Nature draws unobserved which party receives the exploitation opportunity; this assignment is disclosed neither to the parties nor to the mechanism before the deposit and is learned only privately – by the holder from the choice node (Stage 2), by the counterparty through suffering D (Stage 3). The symmetry of the stakes in Stage 1 reflects this veil, not an already-realized role. The game form:

Stage 1. Entry. Each party may join. On joining it posts a refundable stake b . Locked capital bears an opportunity cost εb , with $\varepsilon \geq 0$ small.

Stage 2. Action. The player with the opportunity chooses X or C. The mechanism observes nothing.

Stage 3. Forfeiture. Pressing proceeds in two moments: (3a) both parties simultaneously decide whether to press; (3b) a party whose stake was destroyed at (3a) and whose counterparty’s stake still stands may press once more – the counterstrike node, where the probability q below lives. If i presses: j ’s stake b is destroyed, a share αb is transferred to i , the remainder $(1 - \alpha)b$ is burned, and i pays c ; i ’s own stake, if it still stands, is returned at settlement. Destruction events are observed by the parties and the executor as events; within a match attribution is trivial and harmless, since nothing links identities across matches.

Stage 4. Settlement. All remaining stakes are returned.

The canonical design is *full destruction*, $\alpha = 0$; Prop. 6 treats general α .

Definition 1 (Self-Cost Ratio, Leverage, Effectiveness). $\lambda := c/b \in (0, 1)$ is the fraction of one’s own stake that a presser burns in order to destroy the counterparty’s entire stake; $L :=$

$1/\lambda = b/c > 1$ is the *leverage*. L is at the same time the *effectiveness* of the punishment in the sense of the experimental literature: the factor by which the sanction lowers the target's income (relative to the punisher's cost).

3.3 Payoffs

By symmetry we consider the realization in which i holds the opportunity; the following payoff analysis conditions on this role realization, the case in which j holds being its mirror image. Normalize cooperation (with refunded stakes) to 0 and neglect ε except where noted. If i chooses X and j presses in response, i keeps G but loses the stake b , while j bears the suffered harm D , obtains psychic benefit ψ_j , and pays c materially (recovering αb under α):

$$(i \text{ exploits, } j \text{ presses): } u_i = G - b, \quad u_j = \psi_j - c + \alpha b - D;$$

$$(i \text{ exploits, } j \text{ does not): } u_i = G, \quad u_j = -D;$$

$$(i \text{ cooperates): } u_i = u_j = 0.$$

Note: i , the exploiter, is the *target* of any press; the self-cost c never enters i 's payoff. This separation drives the analysis. At the press node the harm D is materially sunk – it imposes no further cost there – and in the baseline it enters the press comparison only through the disposition, one pressing exactly when $\psi_j - c + \alpha b \geq 0$ with $\psi_j = \psi_j(D, N)$; separately, D drives the participation and selection calculus (Prop. 4).

Finiteness and Counterstrikes. Pressing destroys the counterparty's stake and costs c ; it *does not protect* one's own stake – there is no first-strike immunity (otherwise an exploiter would escape the sanction by pre-emptive pressing). Since only two stakes exist and a destroyed stake is no longer a target, *at most two* destructions occur, and the two-moment structure of Stage 3 closes the game tree after (3b) by game form; an infinite regress of counter- and counter-counterstrikes is mechanically excluded, with no assumption required. A counterstrike therefore need not be *forbidden*, only *priced in*: if the sanctioned exploiter strikes back at (3b) with probability q , the victim's effective self-cost rises from c to $c + qb$ (it additionally risks its own stake), and the deterrence condition retains the form $bp(c + qb) > G$ – a *retaliation tax* that creates, like high- G types, a harder-to-deter subpopulation, but breaks no principle. Under Assumption 2 the canonical case is $q = 0$ – the disposition responds to wrongful harm, and a sanction answering one's own X is, under the prevailing norm, no wrong; materially a counterstrike is loss-making anyway ($-c < 0$) – while the counter-punishment evidence cited there anchors how far q may deviate; the model degrades gradually in q , never discontinuously. The counterstrike's self-cost is moreover a design parameter of its own: a higher self-cost ratio for the strike-back shrinks the counter-striker subpopulation and preserves deterrence under $q > 0$. Externally motivated malice (β) is treated in §5, together with a depth-dependent refinement as an open design direction.

4 Analysis

4.1 Credibility Rests on Disposition Alone

The impossibility result below quantifies over commitment technologies, so we first fix the game they live in and say what a technology *is*. Embed $M(b, c, \alpha)$ in an *extended game*: at a Stage 0 preceding entry, each party simultaneously adopts at most one device (Definition 2; a normalization, not a restriction – Prop. 1(a),(c)) at its sunk cost; adoption is unobserved by the counterparty – the game form contains no signalling stage, and direct pre-play talk babbles (§3) – while publicly observable adoption is treated inside the proof of Theorem 1. The device class

itself is not curated but derived from the regime’s informational primitive: the Stage-2 action is observed by no one but the actor, the suffered harm by no one but the victim, and neither is verifiable to any third party or artifact. The essential constraint is informational: blindness restricts what any engineered trigger can see.

Definition 2 (Self-Binding Device). A *device* is a quadruple $\delta = (\mathcal{G}_\delta, M_\delta, \sigma_\delta, \tau_\delta)$, adopted at Stage 0 at sunk cost $k_\delta \geq 0$: a message space M_δ , a binding press rule σ_δ , and a *holder-payment rule* $\tau_\delta \geq 0$ – abort fees, stand-down penalties, forfeitable bonds – both rules measurable with respect to the trigger information \mathcal{G}_δ and the realized messages. By the informational primitive above, \mathcal{G}_δ is generated by public events – calendar time, the device’s own randomization, realized destruction events – and everything else a device can listen to is *talk*: voluntary, unverifiable messages of its holder or of the counterparty. It contains neither the Stage-2 action nor the suffered harm. Payments *to* a presser exist only through the bound executor, the sole entity that observes presses; we write $s \geq 0$ for this press-conditioned subsidy. Triggers on public events, conditioning on unverifiable talk, money on the holder (τ_δ), money on the press (s): the class exhausts what engineering can attach to a press *on the contractible algebra of this regime* – public events, destructions, and talk are all that the informational primitive leaves verifiable – and Prop. 1 verifies its closure under portfolios, adoption timing, joint adoption, insurance of the destroyed, and exhibition. What a fuller claim would add – a formal language for “institution” beyond this algebra – we do not supply: the algebra itself *is* the exhaustiveness claim, stated as such (§5).

Lemma 1 (Blind Triggers: Action-Invariance or Repriced Discretion). *Fix any profile of devices and subsidies. For a holder with discretion, let τ^p and τ^\emptyset denote the smallest device payments on a press and on a no-press continuation reachable through her messages, and define the induced press differential $\Delta := s + \tau^\emptyset - \tau^p$. In every equilibrium, a device-induced press is of one of two kinds: (i) triggered by an event whose probability is invariant to the Stage-2 choice between X and C; or (ii) contingent on the holder’s own messages, in which case she retains effective discretion and presses exactly when $\psi \geq c - \Delta$ – the harm-contingent channel of Theorem 1(a) below, repriced, not a separate one. Counterparty messages found no third kind.*

Proof. Public events: calendar time and device randomization are exogenous, hence action-invariant. Destruction events: absent gratuitous pressing, the potential exploiter himself never presses in equilibrium – after X as after C, pressing protects nothing and yields a strictly negative payoff – and where he does press, it is at the counterstrike node after a β -press on his own stake (Assumption 2), an event invariant to his Stage-2 choice; either way his Stage-3 behavior carries no information about that choice (at the canonical $q = 0$; a counter-striking exploiter is the priced-in case of §3 and creates no engineered channel either, since his press follows his own disposition, not a device). Conditioning on the holder’s *own* press is void, since the counterparty’s stake can be destroyed at most once. Counterparty messages: they are costless and unverifiable, and their sender strictly prefers whichever message minimizes the probability of being pressed; she sends it after X exactly as after C, so any press conditioned on them is action-invariant – kind (i). Holder messages: the truth of a harm report is verifiable by no one – non-report after harm is undetectable, report without harm unfalsifiable – so no device can bind its holder to *truthful* reporting; the holder chooses among the continuations her messages induce. Payments conditioned on events her choice does not affect cancel from that comparison; what remains is the best press continuation, $\psi - c + s - \tau^p$, against the best no-press continuation, $-\tau^\emptyset$, and sequential rationality gives press $\iff \psi \geq c - \Delta$: kind (ii). A device admitting no no-press continuation leaves its holder no discretion, and its trigger falls under kind (i); one admitting no press continuation never presses and is irrelevant. \square

Proposition 1 (Closure of the Device Class). *The class of Definition 2 is closed under the natural extensions of the instrumentation stage; none finds a press channel beyond the two kinds of Lemma 1.*

- (a) Portfolios. *Finitely many devices held by one party compose to a single device: the product of the message spaces, the join of the trigger information, the sum of the payment rules, the union of the press rules – the last without interaction, since the counterparty’s stake burns at most once. “At most one device” is a normalization, not a restriction.*
- (b) Timing. *Adoption at any later date adds nothing: no new verifiable event accrues over time except destructions, already inside \mathcal{G}_δ ; after suffered harm the holder in any case retains her own press at c , so a late device only shifts Δ within kind (ii); and adoption being unobserved, its date cannot signal.*
- (c) Joint adoption. *A device contracted by both parties is a pair of press and payment rules on the same restricted algebra plus both message streams, and it founds no third kind. Counterparty messages babble as in Lemma 1; inter-party transfers conditioned on messages are, in equilibrium, invariant to the Stage-2 choice and cancel from the margin; what a message can carry is its sender’s own press decision where the joint device grants him one – kind (ii), repriced by whatever the schedule attaches. Mutual knowledge of the joint device is the exhibition case of (e). The instructive instance is the mutual-signature escrow of §2: releasing only on both signatures makes withholding one’s signature the press – a holder discretion whose effective self-cost is one’s own stake, kind (ii) repriced upward to $b > c$, strictly weaker than the mechanism’s own press.*
- (d) Payments to the destroyed. *The bound executor observes destructions, so a payment $z \geq 0$ to a party whose stake was destroyed is contractible – insurance against being pressed. It does not touch the channel; it inflates the temptation:*

$$G - p(b - z) = (G + pz) - pb,$$

so an insured exploiter faces the original margin at the inflated gain $G + pz$. Self-funded at an actuarially fair premium, the transformation is payoff-neutral for a risk-neutral holder and the margin is invariant; third-party funded, it is a subsidy for being sanctioned – G -inflation, against which no stake-based deterrent ever claimed protection and which the condition $b > G/p$ prices like any larger G .

- (e) Exhibition. *Publicly observable adoption adds no kind: an exhibited device deters only through the repricing of its holder’s discretion, the case treated inside the proof of Theorem 1(c).*

Proof. (a) The composite quadruple is a device: $M = \prod_k M_k$, $\mathcal{G} = \bigvee_k \mathcal{G}_k$, $\tau = \sum_k \tau_k$; for the press rule take the pointwise union – a stake destroyed by one rule is no longer a target of another, so no interaction term arises. (b) \mathcal{G}_δ at any date is generated by the same public events; the holder’s post-harm continuation set already contains press and no-press at c , so a device adopted then enters only through Δ ; unobserved adoption is measurable with respect to no other player’s information. (c) The counterparty-message step of the proof of Lemma 1 applies verbatim to the second message stream. For transfers: a message-conditioned transfer schedule gives its sender, at the message node, a ranking of messages independent of his Stage-2 choice – the choice is sunk and invisible to the schedule – so his optimal message, hence the transfer, is the same after X and after C, and a constant cancels from $\mathbb{E}u(X) - \mathbb{E}u(C)$; where the message additionally triggers a press, it is the sender’s own press decision, kind (ii). (d) The displayed identity is arithmetic; the premium, paid at Stage 0, is action-invariant and cancels likewise. (e) Restates the exhibition step of the proof of Theorem 1(c). \square

Proposition 2 (No Deterrence without Disposition). *Under full destruction ($\alpha = 0$): if no player has a retaliatory disposition ($\psi \equiv 0$) and no device (Definition 2) is in place, then no press is ever sequentially rational, exploitation brings its full gain G , and the stake is behaviorally inert.*

Proof. Pressing yields, materially, $-c < 0$ and, with $\psi = 0$, no psychic benefit; a payoff maximizer therefore never presses. Anticipating $p = 0$, an exploiter's payoff is $G - 0 \cdot b = G$, independent of b . The stake is never at risk on any path. \square

Theorem 1 (Credibility: No Substitute for Disposition). *Fix the blind, anonymous, one-shot, arbiter-free regime, extended by the instrumentation Stage 0 above. Allow each player to adopt any device in the closed class (Definition 2, Prop. 1) at arbitrary cost – including holder-payment rules such as stand-down penalties – and allow any press-conditioned subsidy $s \geq 0$ – a transfer share αb , a bounty, a device-side reward – to be paid to a presser through the bound executor, the only entity that observes presses. Untargeted β -pressing is bookkept separately (Prop. 7) and re-enters as on-path action-invariant mass in Cor. 1. Then in every equilibrium of the extended game:*

- (a) Harm-contingent channel. *An injured player presses iff $\psi \geq c_{\text{eff}}$, where $c_{\text{eff}} := c - \Delta$ and $\Delta \geq 0$ is the induced press differential of Lemma 1 ($\Delta = s$ under executor subsidies alone; $\Delta = 0$ bare); the harm-contingent press frequency is $p(c_{\text{eff}}) = \Pr(\psi \geq c_{\text{eff}})$.*
- (b) Erosion, not addition. *Every press not conditioned on the suffered harm occurs with equal probability after X and after C; a stake burns at most once, so such presses do not add to the deterrence margin – they preempt it. Writing r for their probability against the opportunity holder,*

$$\Pr(\text{stake destroyed} \mid X) = 1 - (1 - r)(1 - p(c_{\text{eff}})), \quad \Pr(\text{stake destroyed} \mid C) = r,$$

so the exploiter's margin is

$$\mathbb{E}u(X) - \mathbb{E}u(C) = G - (1 - r)p(c_{\text{eff}})b.$$

Non-contingent pressing contributes nothing to deterrence and, for $r > 0$, strictly erodes it.

- (c) No substitution, repricing only. *Deterrence requires $p(c_{\text{eff}}) > 0$: a positive mass of genuine disposition at the effective threshold. Admissibility – pressing must remain strictly unprofitable for unharmed or undisposed parties, else pressing turns indiscriminate and, by (b), strictly counterproductive – requires $\Delta < c$, hence $c_{\text{eff}} > 0$. Engineered instruments therefore act only by repricing the disposition's expression from c to c_{eff} , whether the money sits on the press (the executor-routed subsidy s) or on the abstention (a device that presses by default unless its holder pays an abort fee π implements $\Delta = \pi$ without touching the executor); with $\Pr(\psi > 0) = 0$ no configuration of devices and subsidies deters.*
- (d) No reputation, no automation. *A standing reputation for pressing requires persistent identity, removed by anonymity; a mechanism-side rule triggering “upon harm” requires observing the action, removed by blindness.*

Credibility therefore rests on genuine, anticipated disposition (Assumption 1) alone: everything engineered can reprice its expression, nothing can replace it – and everything action-blind only thins the margin.

Proof. Throughout, the exploiter chooses at Stage 2 without any pre-action observation of the counterparty: the game form has no signalling stage and the symmetric stake carries no type information (§3).

(a) A press by the harmed player carries no consequence beyond the current match (one-shot) and attaches to no identity (anonymous); against the best no-press continuation its payoff differential is $\psi - c + s - \tau^P + \tau^\emptyset = \psi - (c - \Delta)$ (belief-independent, §3; Lemma 1). Sequential

rationality gives $\text{press} \iff \psi \geq c - \Delta = c_{\text{eff}}$,² whence $p(c_{\text{eff}}) = \Pr(\psi \geq c_{\text{eff}})$. The transfer share of Prop. 6 is the canonical executor-routed instance $\Delta = s = \alpha b$.

(b) Consider any press not conditioned on the suffered harm. By Lemma 1 its trigger is measurable with respect to action-invariant events, so it strikes the opportunity holder's stake with the same probability r whether he chose X or C. The stake is destroyed at most once; after X it survives only if neither the invariant channel nor the harm-contingent channel fires, giving the displayed probabilities and the margin $G - (1-r)p(c_{\text{eff}})b$. The expression is invariant to the within-stage resolution order: whichever channel resolves first, the stake's survival probability after X is $(1-r)(1-p(c_{\text{eff}}))$ either way. If a binding device replaces its holder's discretion outright, that holder's harm-contingent channel is simply off and contributes zero – the same erosion in different bookkeeping. Such pressing is severity without contingency: it punishes the cooperator exactly as often as the exploiter, and what falls on both alike deters neither – while preempting the press that would.

(c) By (b), only the harm-contingent channel of (a) enters the margin positively, which favors cooperation iff $(1-r)p(c_{\text{eff}})b > G$, requiring $p(c_{\text{eff}}) > 0$. For the bound on Δ : an unharmed or undisposed presser nets $\Delta - c$ relative to her best abstention; at $\Delta > c$ pressing is *strictly* profitable for everyone – equivalently, under a stand-down penalty $\pi > c$, abstention is strictly dearer than pressing – hence action-independent, strictly deterrence-eroding by (b), and destructive of cooperators' stakes: externally motivated pressing in the sense of Prop. 7, not a credibility channel; at $\Delta = c$ indifference makes the tie-breaking arbitrary, and we exclude the knife-edge by requiring strictness. (The counterstrike bound of §5 raises an unharmed presser's true break-even to $c + p_\beta b$, so keeping $\Delta < c$ is conservative.) Admissible designs thus keep $\Delta < c$, so $c_{\text{eff}} > 0$ and $p(c_{\text{eff}}) \leq \Pr(\psi > 0)$: no instrument manufactures a press from a population without disposition. It remains to check that no device is privately adopted to shift p beyond this. Concealed, a device is unobservable to the exploiter, confers no private deterrence on its holder, and acts only as a non-excludable externality on the pool frequency; self-funded adoption is strictly dominated for every holder, whatever the others do – a fortiori here, since any action-invariant mass r it contributes strictly erodes, by (b), the very margin its holder relies on. Exhibition is foreclosed by the game form (no signalling stage); and even were adoption publicly observable, by (b) an exhibited device deters only insofar as it lowers its holder's effective press cost – repricing within $\Delta < c$, never a substitute. A bounty bypassing the executor founders on anonymity, the presser being unidentifiable to outsiders; routed through the executor, it *is* the subsidy s , already inside Δ .

(d) Reputation conditions on past presses, which requires linking identities across interactions; anonymity forecloses this. A mechanism-side rule conditioning on the action requires observing it; blindness forecloses this. Both, were they available, would still act on the margin only through (a)–(b). Finally, the quantifier is not vacuous: the no-device profile is optimal at Stage 0 (adoption is strictly dominated, (c)), and the base game then admits the equilibrium of Prop. 3. \square

Corollary 1 (Dilution by Externally Motivated Pressing). *The erosion in (b) is not hypothetical. Let m_β denote the probability that the opportunity holder's counterparty is an externally motivated type who presses (§5, Prop. 7), and let $p = p(c)$ be the harm-contingent frequency among the rest. A β -press strikes whether the holder chose X or C, so it is on-path action-invariant mass, and the pool-level deterrence condition reads*

$$(1 - m_\beta)p(c)b > G,$$

with $b > G/p$ its $m_\beta \rightarrow 0$ limit. The β -residual of §5 thus not only exposes cooperators; it thins

²At $\psi = c_{\text{eff}}$ the player is indifferent; we assume the distribution of ψ is atomless on $(0, \infty)$, so this is a measure-zero event. An atom at $\psi = 0$ – the undisposed mass – is permitted throughout; it is the quantity the frontier of Cor. 2 prices.

deterrence itself – one more reason to bound it. We write the $m_\beta \rightarrow 0$ form throughout and flag the dilution where it binds.

Corollary 2 (The Engineering Frontier). *Fix the extended game of Theorem 1, let ψ be atomless on $(0, \infty)$, and let $M_\beta = 0$. For a temptation G there exists an admissible instrumentation profile under which exploitation is deterred if and only if*

$$b \Pr(\psi > 0) > G.$$

The stake times the mass of the disposition at zero is thus the exact possibility frontier of engineering: repricing pushes the harm-contingent frequency along the disposition’s own distribution, $p(c_{\text{eff}}) \uparrow \Pr(\psi > 0)$ as $\Delta \uparrow c$, and nothing pushes past it. With $M_\beta > 0$ the frontier bends inward: an executor-routed subsidy that cheapens the marginal victim’s press cheapens the β -press identically, so the pressing- β mass $m_\beta(\Delta)$ is nondecreasing in Δ and the operative margin $(1 - m_\beta(\Delta)) p(c - \Delta) b$ (Cor. 1) need not rise to the corner: optimal repricing generically trades the recruitment of the marginal victim against the recruitment of malice at an interior $\Delta^ < c$.*

Proof. (If.) Take the device-free profile with executor subsidy $s = \Delta = c - \epsilon$ and $r = 0$. By Theorem 1(a) the margin is $G - p(\epsilon) b$, and $p(\epsilon) = \Pr(\psi \geq \epsilon) \uparrow \Pr(\psi > 0)$ as $\epsilon \downarrow 0$ by continuity from above; under $b \Pr(\psi > 0) > G$ some $\epsilon > 0$ deters. (Only if.) In every equilibrium the margin is $G - (1 - r) p(c_{\text{eff}}) b$ with $r \geq 0$ (Theorem 1(b)) and, by admissibility, $c_{\text{eff}} > 0$ (Theorem 1(c)), whence $(1 - r) p(c_{\text{eff}}) \leq \Pr(\psi \geq c_{\text{eff}}) \leq \Pr(\psi > 0)$: at $b \Pr(\psi > 0) \leq G$ no admissible configuration makes the margin negative. For $M_\beta > 0$: an unharmed β -presser nets $\beta + \Delta - c - p_\beta b$ against abstention (counterstrike bound, §5), so the pressing mass is nondecreasing in Δ ; it enters as action-invariant $r = m_\beta(\Delta)$ exactly as in Cor. 1. \square

Theorem 1 is the heart of the paper, and its force lies in the erosion result (b). Under blindness, any press an engineered instrument can produce is conditioned on events the exploiting action never touches; it falls on exploiter and cooperator alike, adds nothing to the exploitation margin, and preempts the press that would – engineered severity without harm-contingency is worse than noise: it thins deterrence. This locates the verdicts precisely. The *exhibited* device fails not because its display would be disbelieved – an unconditional auto-press contraption can be perfectly verifiable – but because its trigger cannot see what would need punishing; verifiability is beside the point once the trigger is blind (already under merely *noisy* observation, engineered commitment loses its value (Bagwell, 1995); here the failure sits one layer deeper, in the trigger, not the audience). The *concealed* device fails for the classical reason: a non-excludable externality on the pool that no self-interested party funds. And the transfer share α of Prop. 6 is no counterexample but part (c) at work: engineering *repricing* the one genuine channel, never replacing it – as is the stand-down-penalty device of Theorem 1(c), money on the abstention instead of the press. Harm-contingency is available only to the one party who privately knows the harm, and genuine disposition is an *exogenous* population trait (Assumption 1) that the exploiter rationally anticipates *without* observing it: credibility operates not by being shown but by being statistically expected – and only of a channel that actually exists in the pool. Disposition is itself a commitment in Frank’s sense, but it commits through a *genuine preference* rather than an external binding – which is exactly why it survives where every binding fails: it is the only trigger that conditions on the harm. What remains is what the experimental literature documents: the injured party must *actually* be disposed to retaliate. Everything else – deterrence condition, self-selection, destruction – builds on this. Henceforth we write $p = p(c)$, the conservative canonical value at $\Delta = 0$.

The same result admits a constructive reading, and it is the design point: the invariance is one-sided, and exactly this one-sidedness is the security property – the channel that carries deterrence is closed to money from above, every action-blind press strictly drains it, and the

ceiling is exact, $b \Pr(\psi > 0)$ (Cor. 2). Blindness is thus not an infirmity the mechanism survives but its instrument; the design reading is developed in §6.

4.2 The Deterrence Lemma

Lemma 2 (Deterrence: Neutralization and Effectiveness). *Against a counterparty who presses with probability p , the expected payoff of a potential exploiter from X is $G - pb$, versus 0 from C. Hence:*

- (i) *exploitation is deterred exactly when $pb > G$, i.e. $b > G/p$;*
- (ii) *at $b = G/p$ exploitation is neutralized (expected payoff 0);*
- (iii) *the self-cost c does not enter the exploiter's payoff; c acts only through $p = p(c)$.*

Claims (i)–(iii) are population-level statements in the aggregate frequency p ; the following display changes level and is type-wise. At the type level – against a surely-pressing counterparty ($p = 1$, i.e. $\psi \geq c$) – deterrence holds exactly when $b > G$; together with the willingness condition $c \leq \psi$, the design ratio satisfies

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{b} < \frac{\psi}{G} \quad \iff \quad G < L\psi.$$

This inequality is the necessary consequence of the two operative conditions ($c \leq \psi$ and $b > G$), not their substitute; it makes the leverage visible. Across the choice of the stake b (at fixed λ , i.e. $c = \lambda b$), $L\psi$ is an existence bound: any temptation $G < L\psi$ can be deterred, because there exists an admissible stake $b \in (G, \psi/\lambda]$ that satisfies both $b > G$ (deterrence) and $c = \lambda b \leq \psi$ (willingness). For a fixed (b, c) , by contrast, $b > G/p$ remains the deterrence condition – at fixed λ , a b that is too small does not deter a temptation $b < G < L\psi$ (cf. the partiality in Prop. 4). The effectiveness $L = 1/\lambda$ is the factor by which one unit of anticipated anger scales the maximal deterrable temptation.

Proof. Arithmetic from the payoffs. For the displayed inequality: $c \leq \psi \Rightarrow c/b \leq \psi/b$, and $b > G \Rightarrow \psi/b < \psi/G$; hence $c/b < \psi/G$. Equivalently $b/c > G/\psi$, i.e. $L > G/\psi$, i.e. $G < L\psi$. \square

Remark 1 (Plausibility Anchor, Not Proof). Here λ (equivalently L) does work rather than appearing as a passive quotient. For illustration let $\lambda = 4/15$, so $L = 3.75$ – above the experimental effectiveness threshold (§2); the value is illustrative and author-chosen, not independent evidence, and that threshold is a multi-player anchor, not measured in the bilateral case. One thing the mechanism itself contributes here: it specifies its own measurement protocol. Each press decision is a *censored observation* of the disposition at the effective threshold – a press reveals $\psi \geq c_{\text{eff}}$, a non-press $\psi < c_{\text{eff}}$ – and since c is a design parameter, exogenous variation of the self-cost across controlled treatments traces the curve $p(c)$ pointwise, closing precisely the bilateral gap left open above. The identification is clean only where exploitation is experimentally induced: in field operation the observed press rate is a mixture, $\Pr(\text{press}) = \Pr(X)p(c_{\text{eff}})$ plus the ε - and β -shares of Prop. 7, and – as Assumption 3 records – most informative off the deterring path. The bilateral magnitude of $p(c)$ is thus not merely missing evidence but a designed experiment awaiting execution.

Note that b and c play distinct roles – b fixes how hard the exploiter is hit, c fixes how cheaply (and thus, via $p(c)$, how probably) the injured party presses – and $\lambda = c/b$ is their unavoidable coupling. Two comparative statics must be separated here. *At fixed c* (hence falling λ : harder sanction per unit of anger) a larger b raises the deterrence margin $p(c)b$ monotonically – more stake deters unambiguously more. *At fixed λ* , by contrast, $c = \lambda b$ couples both quantities: a larger b hits the exploiter harder but at the same time raises $c = \lambda b$ and lowers $p(\lambda b)$; the margin $p(\lambda b)b$ is then not necessarily monotone in b , and the designer chooses b so that $b > G/p(\lambda b)$ holds wherever this is achievable. Where we say below that a larger b strengthens deterrence (Prop. 7(b)), the first static is meant: c – and thus $p(c)$ – stays fixed while b grows. In both

statics the stake required for deterrence scales, per $b > G/p$, like $1/p$: as the disposition in the pool thins ($p \downarrow$), the required stake grows continuously, and the mechanism loses its effect only in the limit $p \rightarrow 0$ (the corner of Prop. 2) – no knife-edge, but gradual degradation.

The Price of Thin Dispositions. The scaling $b > G/p$ must be confronted at realistic frequencies, not merely stated. What the record documents is the disposition’s *existence*; nothing in its second-party, one-shot form suggests press frequencies near one at stake-relevant self-costs. At $p \in [1/5, 1/2]$ the required stake is two to five times the temptation, and the locked-capital cost εb scales with the same multiple: overcollateralization, paid in capital rather than in verification, is the mechanism’s real price. The introduction’s numbers are chosen to show this rather than hide it – $b = 150$ against $G = 70$ at $p = \frac{1}{2}$ – and the same honesty governs the one-sided instance of Remark 2 below, whose required frequency $1/(1+w)$ is scale-free but not small.

The Two Prices, Confronted. The two variants of the construction pay for credibility in different currencies, and the honest exhibit prices them side by side. The symmetric mechanism holds the required frequency at G/b but is exposed to the counterstrike posit of Assumption 2: the threshold stays put while the point on the curve $p(\cdot)$ at which it must be met moves with q – at the quarter-rate that Nikiforakis (2008) documents where counter-punishment is open, to nearly double the nominal self-cost. The one-sided instance closes $q = 0$ by game form and pays in the threshold itself, which falls only as the press budget grows with the ticket.

<i>Symmetric mechanism</i> (anchor $b = 150, c = 40, G = 70$; required: $p(c_{\text{eff}}) > G/b = 7/15 \approx 0.47$)			
counterstrike risk q	0	0.1	0.25
effective self-cost $c_{\text{eff}} = c + qb$	40	55	77.5
<i>One-sided instance</i> (Remark 2; $q = 0$ by game form; required: $p(wT) > 1/(1+w)$)			
wedge w	$2/7$	1	$3/2$
required frequency	$7/9 \approx 0.78$	$1/2$	$2/5$
press budget $c = wT$	$2T/7$	T	$3T/2$

Neither column is free: the symmetric form buys a moderate threshold at counterstrike exposure, the one-sided form buys mechanical $q = 0$ at a steep threshold or a growing press budget. The honest design object is this trade-off, not either instance; and the lever named in §3 – a separate, higher self-cost ratio for the strike-back – buys q down directly, shrinking the counter-striking subpopulation without touching the first press.

Proposition 3 (Existence and Conditional Uniqueness of the Deterrence Equilibrium). *Let Assumption 1 (reality) and Assumption 2 (activation) hold, and let the belief $p = p(c)$ be correct per Assumption 3. Then for every participating pair:*

- (a) Existence. *The strategy profile – the opportunity holder cooperates; an injured player presses exactly when $\psi \geq c$ – is an equilibrium in the above sense, provided $b > G/p$ for the realized temptation G (with externally motivated mass in the pool, Cor. 1 applies).*
- (b) Conditional uniqueness. *The press strategy is uniquely fixed by sequential rationality on $\{\psi \geq c\}$ (a $\psi > c$ type who does not press, or a $\psi < c$ type who presses, violates it). Hence the behavioral outcome is unique on the deterred region $\{G < pb\}$: there, no exploitation occurs. For $G > pb$ the unique outcome is the reverse – exploitation (Prop. 4(c)); the uniqueness of “no exploitation” is thus tied to $b > G/p$ per type G , not a global fact.*

Proof. (a) Against press probability p , the exploitation payoff is $G - pb < 0 =$ the cooperation payoff under $b > G/p$ (Lemma 2); cooperation is thus a best response, and pressing exactly when $\psi \geq c$ is sequentially rational (Theorem 1(a)). (b) The uniqueness of the press strategy

is Theorem 1(a); the case distinction G vs. pb is Lemma 2(i) with Prop. 4(c). The statement takes p as correctly calibrated (Assumption 3); that the participating pool carries exactly this p is the subject of the remark after Prop. 4. \square

Remark 2 (A One-Sided Instance: Payment in Limbo). The symmetric stakes of §3 reflect the veil over roles at entry; no proof above uses that veil for anything else. This licenses an instance in which the veil is absent by construction because the mechanism itself executes a payment: the transfer's direction publicly realizes who can exploit whom. A payer transfers T , which the executor holds in limbo for a window W , and posts a press budget $c = wT$ for a wedge fraction $w \in (0, 1)$, refunded iff unused; the payee posts wT , so the destructible mass on the payee's side is $b = (1 + w)T$; only the payer holds a press.

Settlement to the payee occurs at $\min(\text{payer's consent}, W)$, so silence is delayed consent rather than a hostage; the default must point to the payee, since a refund default would let a payer take the consideration and run out the clock. Stakes are indexed by the transaction (T, w) , not chosen, and thus carry no type information; blindness is untouched, since the executor sees the payment leg it executes but still observes neither the consideration nor the harm.

Three features are then properties of the restriction rather than assumptions. (i) Deleting the payee's press removes an option never exercised in equilibrium (proof of Lemma 1), so the role-conditional payoffs – and hence all on-path incentives – are those of $M((1 + w)T, wT, 0)$, i.e. $\lambda = w/(1 + w)$ and $L = (1 + w)/w$; the destruction bound of §3 tightens from two to one. (ii) The counter-punishment branch that §3 prices and Assumption 2 flags – the retaliation tax $c + qb$ – is closed mechanically: the sanctioned party has no move, so $q = 0$ holds by game form, not by posit. (iii) For exploitation bounded by the transfer – withholding the consideration, so $G \leq T$ – the deterrence condition $b > G/p$ collapses to $p(wT) > 1/(1 + w)$: the *required* frequency is a single scale-free constant across ticket sizes (at $w = 2/7$: $7/9$, with $L = 4.5$ – a required frequency above anything the second-party record documents; realistic frequencies demand a larger wedge, $w = 1$ requiring $p > 1/2$ and $w = 3/2$ requiring $p > 2/5$, at the price of a press budget wT that grows with the ticket), while the *delivered* frequency $p(wT)$ tracks the ticket only insofar as the disposition scales with the harm ($\psi = \psi(D, N)$, §3) – whether it does is part of the measurement protocol above.

The entry logic of Prop. 4 applies with the payee as the potential exploiter, and the β -residual of Prop. 7 concentrates on the payee's side (a malicious payer burns wT to destroy $(1 + w)T$) – and does so *without* the counterstrike self-limit of §5, the payee holding no press: the one-sided form trades that self-limit for the mechanical $q = 0$ of (ii); the one design requirement, flagged as such, is that W exceed the payer's harm-detection time. Everything else is inherited; the instance adds no assumption.

4.3 Self-Selection at Entry: A Consequence of Deterrence

Deterrence has a *consequence* beyond mere behavioral change: it sorts who enters at all. This is not a standalone result but the familiar self-selection at the participation margin, triggered here by the unprofitability from Lemma 2, solely through the agents' outside options.

Proposition 4 (Delegation and Self-Selection at Entry). *Let a player's type be (G, ρ) : his temptation and his outside option (the rent from exploiting an unprotected party elsewhere).*

- (a) Delegation. *Because the mechanism observes nothing, a press is performed only by an injured player with $\psi \geq c$. A player who never exploits never harms anyone and therefore never faces a press on the equilibrium path: the mechanism touches only those it deters.*
- (b) Selection. *Under deterrence $b > G/p$, a player with $G \leq pb$ does not exploit profitably within the mechanism (exploitation payoff $G - pb \leq 0$); a pure exploiter (value only from X) then strictly prefers his outside option and does not enter whenever $\rho > 0$ – his in-*

mechanism payoff is $0 < \rho$. The participating pool excludes pure exploiters with $G \leq pb$ and $\rho > 0$.

- (c) Partiality (qualification). With heterogeneous (G, ρ) , exploiters with $G > pb$ (temptation beyond the stake's reach) are not deterred, and exploiters with $\rho \leq 0$ can enter regardless. Selection is partial, governed by the thresholds G vs. pb and ρ vs. $(G - pb)^+$.

Proof. (a) is immediate from blindness and Theorem 1(a). (b) and (c) follow from Lemma 2 and the comparison of the in-mechanism exploitation payoff $G - pb$ with ρ . \square

Corollary 3 (Displacement Is a Cost, Not a Benefit). *Deterred or excluded exploiters with $\rho > 0$ divert to non-members; the mechanism displaces exploitation rather than eliminating it. The threshold in Prop. 4(b) is easier to satisfy when ρ is large, so that a more predatory environment yields a cleaner pool – but a correspondingly larger externality borne by non-members. The mechanism is a club good that exports the harm it excludes.*

Remark 3 (Self-Selective Pool Enrichment). Lemma 2 takes $p = p(c)$ as the press probability of a random counterparty. Since Prop. 4 makes the pool composition endogenous, one must ask whether the self-selection shifts this p . That depends on the relation between the first-strike disposition ψ (the victim's anger) and the exploitation propensity (G, ρ) . A *negative* correlation is plausible: the gain-motivated exploiter bears no personal grudge against his target – he extracts value and accepts the harm rather than seeking it – and one who calculates this way is, as a victim, also less inclined to costly retaliation (“in his place I would have done the same”). The same character property at the same time carries the exploiter-side content of Assumption 2 – the canonical $q = 0$ (§3): the exploiter does not experience being pressed as a wrong to be avenged; self-serving misperception of the norm is the priced deviation. Under this correlation, selection works *for* deterrence: it disproportionately removes the low-vengeance types at entry, so that the remaining pool is more vengeful and the true pool- p (weakly) dominates the naive p of the overall distribution – deterrence with the overall-distribution threshold is then conservative. Two honesty notes. *First*, the correlation is a psychological conjecture doing double duty – it carries both this enrichment and the canonical $q = 0$ (§3) – and it is a conjecture, not a result. *Second*, the opposite sign cannot be excluded: were vengefulness positively associated with exploitation propensity (spite and predation travelling together), selection would thin the disposition, the pool- p would fall below the naive p , and deterrence would need a larger stake than the overall distribution suggests. The induced fixed point – pool $\rightarrow p \rightarrow$ selection \rightarrow pool – is made precise in Prop. 5 for either sign: a self-consistent, calibrated p^* exists regardless; the sign decides only whether T is increasing (favourable case, possibly multiple fixed points) or decreasing (adverse case, in which the fixed point is *unique*, since a decreasing continuous self-map of $[0, 1]$ crosses the diagonal exactly once).

The Numbers, Recalled. For the introduction's values ($b = 150$, $c = 40$, so $\lambda = 4/15$, $L = 3.75$; $G = 70$, $D = 70$; $p = \frac{1}{2}$ at $c = 40$), Prop. 4 reads off immediately: the Stefan type never presses and leaves at 0; the Gabi type computes $G - pb = -5 < 0 \leq \rho$ and stays away (Prop. 4(b)), so on the equilibrium path no press ever occurs.

Remark 4 (Invisible Exclusion). The self-selection operates *before* any interaction. The protected party therefore does not encounter the excluded exploiter and sees no stream of repelled attempts either; it draws from a pool that the exploiter never even entered. This is a compositional, not merely a deterrent, effect: the mechanism changes not the behavior of a present exploiter but *who is present at all*. The statement concerns the composition of the participating pool, not a global epistemic claim: the one sorted out disappears from the experience of this mechanism, not from the world – he migrates, as Cor. 3 records, to unprotected targets.

4.4 Calibration as a Stationary Fixed Point

Assumption 3 took the level of the belief $p(c)$ as the load-bearing fragility (§5). The self-selection of Prop. 4 lets us replace a posited coincidence by an equilibrium-consistency condition. Read the construction not as a lone dyad but as a *stationary population game*: the *pairwise* encounter is one-shot and anonymous – no re-meeting, no legible type, no reputation, so Theorem 1 is untouched – while a continuum population plays it recurrently under anonymous random matching. Then p is the *stationary aggregate* press frequency, the population-wide rate at which harmed parties retaliate; a press destroys an observed stake even as the presser stays anonymous, so this frequency is *public* and learnable in the aggregate *without* any individual reputation. Aggregate knowledge of a base rate is categorically different from reputation: it lets no exploiter pick out a yielding individual, so the inescapability of the threat (Theorem 1, the indeterminacy of the single counterparty) is preserved. Recurrent anonymous matching is, at the same time, the habitat of *community enforcement*: cooperation sustained without identities by contagion, a defection triggering spreading defection that punishes the original defector through his own future matches (Kandori, 1992; Ellison, 1994). This rational, disposition-free channel lives in exactly the population frame just introduced and must be dispatched, not ignored. It has no grip on our margin, for the reason Prop. 4 supplies: contagion disciplines only agents with continuation value *inside* the pool, and the marginal exploiter is precisely the hit-and-run type whose outside option ρ prices his exit. Nor need participants be long-lived: the belief $p(c)$ feeds on the aggregate record, not on personal re-encounters, so entrants may play once and leave. Where contagion’s preconditions hold – patient, pool-bound agents – the commitment problem this paper addresses does not arise in full force; our domain is its complement.

Let a type be $\theta = (\psi, G, \rho, v)$ with an atomless joint distribution, where $v \geq 0$ is the *access value* – the benefit the agent attaches to a successful, unexploited interaction. Prop. 7(c) declares this quantity an exogenous model boundary, and we keep that discipline: v enters exactly once, as an *entry hypothesis*, not as a modeled object. A cooperator enters when v exceeds a *reservation exposure* $\bar{e}(p)$, a continuous function of the aggregate press frequency alone, which we take as the primitive reduced form of his exposure calculus. (Its microfoundation would evaluate the bound of Prop. 7(c) at the equilibrium pool itself; endogenizing that adds an inner fixed point in the cooperator mass – exposure falls as cooperators enter, so the inner entry map is monotone and existence follows from Knaster–Tarski – whose selections need not vary continuously in p . Nothing downstream uses the refinement, so we keep the reduced form and say so.) The mass of externally motivated entrants is an exogenous constant $M_\beta \geq 0$ (Prop. 7(c)), outside θ as outside the model. A pure exploiter compares $\max(G - pb, 0)$ with his outside option ρ (Prop. 4). At a prevailing press frequency p , entry is thus individually rational for a measurable set $E(p)$ of (ψ, G, ρ, v) -types, and the harm-contingent frequency the *entering* pool then generates is

$$T(p) = \Pr(\psi \geq c \mid \theta \in E(p)).$$

A *calibrated stationary press frequency* is a fixed point $p^* = T(p^*)$: what agents anticipate equals what their entry decisions produce.

Proposition 5 (Existence of a Calibrated Stationary Press Frequency). *Suppose types $\theta = (\psi, G, \rho, v)$ are atomless, entry follows the threshold rules above with $\bar{e}(\cdot)$ continuous, and a positive mass of cooperators has $v > \bar{e}(p)$ at every p , so that the entering mass is bounded away from zero. Then $T : [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous and has a fixed point $p^* = T(p^*)$. At p^* the calibration of Assumption 3 holds endogenously: the anticipated frequency is exactly the one the participating pool generates.*

Proof. T takes values in $[0, 1]$, being a conditional probability. The entry set $E(p)$ is delimited by the threshold loci $\{G = pb\}$, $\{\rho = (G - pb)^+\}$, and $\{v = \bar{e}(p)\}$; each locus moves continuously in p and, under an atomless joint distribution, carries measure zero. As $p_n \rightarrow p$, the indicator of

$E(p_n)$ converges to that of $E(p)$ off these null sets, so by dominated convergence both the mass of $E(p)$ and the mass of $\{\psi \geq c\} \cap E(p)$ are continuous in p ; with the entering mass bounded away from 0, the quotient T is continuous. A continuous self-map of $[0, 1]$ has a fixed point – Brouwer, or the intermediate value theorem applied to $g(p) = T(p) - p$, which satisfies $g(0) \geq 0$ and $g(1) \leq 0$. The exogenous mass M_β enters the matching shares but not T ; with the entering mass bounded away from zero, $m_\beta(p) = M_\beta / (M_\beta + |E(p)|)$ is continuous as well, so the diluted condition of Cor. 1 is well-posed at p^* . \square

This converts the headline reduction from a coincidence into a consistency requirement: credibility rests on disposition (Theorem 1), and the level of p at which the threat bites is a fixed point of the pool composition, not an external gift. What the result does *not* settle we state plainly. It yields *existence*, not *uniqueness*: under the negative ψ –(G, ρ) assortment of Rem. 3, T can be increasing and several fixed points may coexist – a low- p regime in which weak deterrence sustains an exploiter-rich pool, and a high- p regime in which self-selection enriches it. Nor does it show that a *learning dynamic* on the public aggregate converges to a given p^* . Which fixed point is selected, and whether aggregate experience reaches it, is open problem (1) – now sharpened from “where does calibration come from” to “which calibrated fixed point, and along which dynamics.”

From Frequency to Content. The fixed point p^* takes the norm – what counts as the wrong that activates ψ – as given and asks only *how often* a settled wrong is avenged. A prior fixed point governs the *content* of the norm itself: a *constituted norm* is an $N^* = R(N^*)$ whose wrongs are exactly the action-types that are, when suffered, in fact avenged often enough to deter, given that the population holds N^* and that disposition scales as $\psi = \psi(D, N)$. Its formal treatment – existence and structure of such fixed points on the lattice of norm sets – requires a monotonicity of the retaliation response in the prevailing norm that we do not defend here; it belongs to separate work and to the constitutive open problem (1). What the present paper fixes is the conditional claim: *given* a constituted N^* and the induced p^* , the mechanism protects.

4.5 Destruction as a No-Profit Condition

Proposition 6 (Why Burn, and How Much). *Under transfer share α , a press yields its performer, materially, $\alpha b - c$.*

- (a) No-profit condition. *Pressing is non-profitable for a player without disposition ($\psi = 0$) exactly when $\alpha b \leq c$, i.e. $\alpha \leq \lambda$. For strict suppression of gratuitous pressing – so that only $\psi > 0$ players ever press – require $\alpha < \lambda$; full destruction $\alpha = 0$ is the canonical strict point.*
- (b) The decoupling trade-off. *Within $[0, \lambda)$ a higher α grants the injured party a partial compensation αb while preserving the no-profit property (the decoupling principle of Polinsky & Che (1991): what the victim receives need not equal what the injurer loses); but it lowers the cost of externally motivated harm, since an injurer recovers αb . Thus $\alpha = 0$ maximizes harm resistance and lets “no value flows between players” hold globally, while $\alpha \uparrow \lambda$ trades resistance for victim compensation.*

Destruction is therefore a justified choice within the admissible no-profit interval, not a necessity.

Proof. Arithmetic. Non-profitability is $\alpha b - c \leq 0 \Leftrightarrow \alpha \leq c/b = \lambda$; strictness replaces \leq by $<$. The comparative static in α is immediate. \square

Any $\alpha < \lambda$ preserves deterrence and no-gratuitousness while compensating the victim, and an $\alpha > 0$ even *strengthens* deterrence (the press threshold falls to $\psi \geq c - \alpha b$, so p rises to $p(c - \alpha b) \geq p(c)$, while the exploiter still risks his full b); the $p = p(c)$ of the deterrence analysis

is thus the conservative $\alpha = 0$ value. In the language of Theorem 1, α is the canonical press-conditioned subsidy $s = \alpha b$, and the no-profit condition $\alpha < \lambda$ is exactly the admissibility bound $\Delta < c$ at its executor-routed instance $\Delta = s = \alpha b$: repricing within the admissible region, never substitution – the transfer share amplifies a disposition that must already exist, and with $\psi \equiv 0$ no α deters. Full destruction is nonetheless canonical for *credibility*: only when no value flows back ($\alpha = 0$) is a press exclusively an expression of disposition, never of gain, so that disposition alone carries the threat and the derived self-selection stays free of a gain motive.

5 Scope: The Truthless Regime and Its Single Residual

The mechanism observes no action, names no wrong, and adjudicates nothing. The distinction “justified press” versus “malicious press” is *not* one it draws or claims to draw; “justified” presupposes an adjudicated truth that the regime does not contain. A press is simply an event that costs the presser c and destroys the target’s stake b ; each player acts on *anticipated press probabilities*, not on adjudicated guilt. This is the operating regime: bilateral interaction without a common notion of truth and without a third-party arbiter – Schelling’s world, not the courtroom. Within it, the mechanism delivers a *unique* behavioral outcome in the sense of Prop. 3: under Assumptions 1–3 and $b > G/p$, the deterred region is not exploited, and the press strategy is unique by sequential rationality. Methodologically the construction is, strictly speaking, not a mechanism of the revelation tradition – there is no social choice function, no type report, no message space – but a game-theoretically analyzed *deterrence mechanism* in the Schelling–Frank line, whose incentive rule we specify in the sense of mechanism design (Maskin, 2008) and whose equilibrium we characterize. We therefore claim *weak* implementation (one equilibrium delivers the desired outcome) and the conditional uniqueness of the on-path outcome stated above, *not* completeness in the sense of general implementation theory (the implementability of an arbitrary social choice function or the elimination of all equilibria).

The common objection that the mechanism “cannot distinguish a deserved press from an abusive one” is thus a category error, not an internal failure: the same blindness that forecloses automation and reputation (Theorem 1) *is* the design.

A corollary of the same theorem constrains the regime’s *own records*. A person-linkable press history – who pressed, how often, against whom – would reconstitute exactly the standing reputation that anonymity removes: pressing would acquire consequences beyond the match, the press would turn strategic, and the blindness that makes the signal honest would erode endogenously at the regime’s own bookkeeping. The public record that Assumption 3 feeds on must therefore be *aggregate and unlinkable* – frequencies, not files; the regime must be blind not only to actions but to the identities in its own archive.

Two Regimes. Where a shared notion of exploitation is in force – ψ responding to a settled norm N – the mechanism is *protection*: Assumptions 1–3 hold by hypothesis and the analysis above applies in full. Where none is, it is the only channel through which one could form – the press being the sole act that marks a move intolerable without an arbiter pronouncing on it; that constitutive case is formulated in §4.4 (*From Frequency to Content*) and marked as open problem (1). The present paper resolves the protective case.

Mechanism-Design Classification. The desiderata of implementation theory line up as follows. *Incentive compatibility* appears not as a revelation condition (nothing is reported) but as *obedience* on the path – the equilibrium actions are best responses (cooperating under deterrence, pressing exactly when $\psi \geq c$), and only partially so, since the non-deterred high- G type ($G > pb$) does not obey. *Budget balance* is deliberately not maintained (value is burned, Prop. 6), but the imbalance is purely *off-path*: on the path nothing is pressed, hence nothing burned, and all stakes are refunded; Myerson & Satterthwaite (1983) rules out ex-post efficient,

budget-balanced, individually rational bilateral trade; we stand outside its scope twice over – no allocation is implemented, and budget balance is deliberately sacrificed, if only off path. *Wilson robustness*: the game form is detail-free – one rule for every prior, depending on no distribution of ψ, G, ρ – but only in *form*, not in *function*, since credibility lives off the correctly calibrated belief $p(c)$ (Assumption 3); detail-freeness of form buys no robustness of outcome. *Executor credibility* requires binding the executing entity to the destruction (§3; Akbarpour & Li, 2020).³

The One Real Residual. An externally motivated party – one who derives an outside benefit $\beta > 0$ (a competitor, a vandal, a spiteful type) from destroying a counterparty’s stake – can, willing to burn c , destroy b . This type is not a theoretical possibility: Falk et al. (2005) document that defectors impose substantial *spiteful* punishment on cooperators, and that such spite persists exactly when punishing improves the punisher’s relative standing – which full destruction does, the target losing b while the presser burns only $c < b$. Unprovoked destruction at own cost is documented in its own right: people pay to reduce others’ incomes absent any wrong (Zizzo & Oswald, 2001), and in the joy-of-destruction game a substantial share destroys when the act is veiled (Abbinck & Sadrieh, 2009) – the residual has a measured magnitude, not merely a name. Under Assumption 2 it is also *self-limiting*: gratuitous destruction is wrongful harm under any norm in whose regime the mechanism protects, so the victim’s capacity activates, and node (3b) hands her the strike back – the β -press puts the presser’s own stake at risk. Writing $p_\beta := \Pr(\psi(b, N) \geq c)$ for the counterstrike frequency among the gratuitously harmed, a β -type presses only if

$$\beta > c + p_\beta b,$$

so the same disposition that carries deterrence taxes malice, thinning the exposure masses of Prop. 7 and Cor. 1 from within. (The one-sided instance of Remark 2 lacks this self-limit – the payee holds no press – a trade its text records.) The residual is thus empirically real, and bounding it, not denying it, is the honest treatment. It violates no claim (the mechanism never promised protection against costly malice); it is a property of the regime, quantifiable and, by the counterstrike bound, self-limiting. The following statement makes it precise and quantifies how *pure* the participating pool is – answering the objection that the mechanism does not make the interaction “safe”: not absolutely, but bounded and measurable.

Proposition 7 (Bounded Exposure of the Non-Exploiter / Purity). *Under Assumptions 1–3 and deterrence $b > G/p$ for the targeted temptation:*

- (a) Purity against gain motivation. *A party that cooperates harms no one and is therefore never pressed on the equilibrium path (Prop. 4(a)); against any deterred or cooperating counterparty its in-mechanism payoff is 0. Gain-motivated exploiters with $G \leq pb$ and $\rho > 0$ have dropped out (Prop. 4(b)).*
- (b) The bounded residual. *The only remaining exposure is to two classes that deterrence at level b does not exclude: extremely tempted exploiters with $G > pb$ (Prop. 4(c)), who exploit and inflict harm D , and externally motivated β -types, who destroy the stake b at self-cost c and, by the counterstrike bound above, at risk $p_\beta b$. The first class shrinks as b rises (larger pb deters more); the second is the irreducible residual – one that, by Cor. 1, simultaneously thins the deterrence margin by the factor $(1 - m_\beta)$, so bounding it protects the cooperator and the condition $b > G/p$ at once.*

³Two further desiderata hold automatically. *Renegotiation-proofness*: ex post both would prefer a deal (the exploiter pays a bribe $x < b$, the victim forgoes pressing if $\psi - c \leq x$), but in an arbiter-free regime the bribe is unenforceable – whoever pays first is then expropriated (the paid victim still presses, since $\psi - c > 0$ remains) – so, anticipated, no deal forms and $p(c)$ stays the relevant probability; the absence of the enforcement that creates the problem secures the threat against ex-post deals. *Collusion* (mutual pressing to skim α -transfers) is unprofitable: each loses his own destroyed stake, $ab - c - b < 0$.

(c) Purity as a measure. “Safety for the non-exploiter” is thus not absolute but bounded and quantifiable: the cooperating party’s expected loss is the probability-weighted exposure to these two classes (plus the capital cost εb). Whether its participation is individually rational depends on whether the value of access – the benefit from a successful, unexploited interaction – exceeds this loss. This access value the present construction deliberately does not model: it normalizes cooperation to 0 and treats only the deterrence side; the access value is an exogenous, declared model boundary, not a derived object. The purity of the pool – the ratio of the honest and deterred share to this residual – is unaffected by it, as is the deterrence condition $b > G/p$.

Proof. (a) is Prop. 4(a),(b). (b): deterred exploiters with $\rho \leq 0$ do enter but generate no exposure – they are deterred and cooperate on the path – so that only the two named classes ($G > pb$ and β) cause harm; (b) is thus the exhaustive complement, for the exposure, to the deterrence and exclusion conditions, together with the β -property of the regime. (c) is the expectation over (a) and (b). \square

The one real residual from (b) is quantifiable.⁴ For the protected party, the expected loss from Prop. 7(c) takes the form

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{loss}] \approx \mu_H D + \mu_\beta b + \varepsilon b$$

where μ_H denotes the probability of encountering a non-deterred high- G type (who inflicts harm D) and μ_β that of encountering an externally motivated β -type (who destroys one’s own stake b); the bound is closed in *form*, its *magnitude* hinging solely on the two type masses μ_H, μ_β (the latter thinned from within by the counterstrike bound above), which the model – like the access value – declares exogenous. “Quantifiable” thus means here: determined up to two openly declared population parameters. On the injurer’s side, under full destruction the attacker burns c per destroyed b – pays λ per destroyed unit of value, equivalently spends $1/L$ of the harm done. Absolute deterrence of such harm is bought by raising b (so that $c = \lambda b$ is absolutely large), at the cost of locked capital. The same effectiveness L that empowers an injured party empowers an injurer; one can eliminate this only by pushing L below the effectiveness threshold – that is, precisely below the range from which punishment sustains cooperation at all. The design therefore accepts the exposure and bounds it rather than eliminating it.

An Open Design Direction. The mechanism is blind to *guilt* but observes its *own* destructions; in principle the self-cost ratio could therefore depend on the press depth (λ_d increasing in d), in order to make later counterstrikes more expensive. We do *not* pursue this here: such a tiered schedule blindly indexes *order*, not *guilt* – an aggressor could strike first to claim the cheap tier, and the schedule would tax exactly the counterstrike the design now welcomes, the gratuitously harmed victim’s response that bounds the β -residual above – and it would threaten to reimport precisely the truth-tracking that the mechanism deliberately forgoes. We mark it as an open direction (open problem (4)), not a result.

Limits of Reach. Two limits must be named. *Bilaterality*: the assumption-free finiteness (at most two destructions) and the canonical case $q = 0$ hinge on the dyad; with $n \geq 3$ parties and n stakes, precisely the regress of counter- and counter-counterstrikes would arise that the two-stake structure mechanically excludes. The mechanism is constitutively bilateral; a generalization upward is not given. *Asymmetry of miscalibration*: deterrence hinges on the

⁴It is *not* freely dampable by redirecting the burn: any destination of the forfeited value is a potential financier of the β -motive – a cause-motivated presser pays c and steers b to “his” cause, an s -free press subsidy that the bookkeeping of Cor. 1 would then have to carry. Admissible destinations are only those that no participant plausibly values at λ or more per unit destroyed; “routing the burn to a public good” is thus a design variable under exactly this constraint, not a free welfare improvement.

correct belief $p(c)$ (Assumption 3), and the error is not symmetric. If the exploiter overestimates p , he is over-deterred – this costs only him. If he underestimates p , he exploits even though the true press probability would have deterred him, and the injured party bears D . The design is thus robust against overestimation, fragile against underestimation of p ; it is not enough that p be correct on average. In the constitutive case (§5) this underestimation is the generic starting condition: a pool in which no norm is yet settled presses rarely, so p begins low and exploitation is not yet deterred – the low- p regime of §4.4 seen locally.

Open Problems. Four gaps remain, none of which the present analysis closes.

- (1) *The constitutive problem: endogenous norm and disposition.* The model takes the norm N and the disposition $\psi = \psi(D, N)$ as given (Assumptions 1, 2) and its frequency-belief as calibrated (Assumption 3). The deeper question is not *how often* a settled wrong is avenged but *whether a wrong becomes settled at all*: whether a constituted norm $N^* = R(N^*)$ (§4.4) exists at all, which one a population reaches, and along which dynamics – the Frank question, now at the level of content rather than frequency. Both selection questions are amenable to computational study in populations of artificial agents, where ψ , c , and the matching structure are controllable primitives – the standard toolkit of evolutionary game theory, applied to a mechanism whose fixed points are already characterized. A meta-game in which agents *choose* whether to build the disposition, its benefit only off-path, could unravel both N and p downward. Related but separate is *commitment stability*: whether an agent who over a long time never comes to press has an interest in shedding the disposition, undermining credibility for all. The dynamics face a structural headwind recorded at Assumption 3: the deterring path itself thins the record they must learn from. These concern the ground on which everything rests, and are the subject of separate work.
- (2) *Partial selection.* Prop. 4(c): with heterogeneous (G, ρ) the pool is not fully clean.
- (3) *Displacement.* Cor. 3: the welfare externality on non-members.
- (4) *Depth-dependent effectiveness.* The tiered λ_d of “An Open Design Direction” (§5), to be secured against first-strike incentives.

6 Discussion

The novelty is configurational and one theorem deep: stakes, costly punishment, commitment, money-burning, and self-selection are individually classical (§2); new are the erosion result – under blindness every engineered press falls on exploiter and cooperator alike, deters neither, and preempts the press that would deter, so engineering can reprice or thin the disposition channel but never replace it (Theorem 1) – and the assembly of the classical parts into a credible deterrence without reputation, whose sole price is the bounded, quantifiable exposure to externally motivated harm (Prop. 7). Put in terms of resources: the construction consumes none of the quantities on which the classical resolutions rest – repetition, identity, verifiable action, compensating transfer (§2) – but two others, both openly priced: bonded capital (εb) and a population-level disposition ($p(c)$). A construction with mutual destruction may exist elsewhere unrecognized by us; we invite refutation by prior art rather than rhetorical defense.

A broader design pattern is visible here, which we name without claiming it as a result. The mechanism does not *correct* a documented behavioral endowment, as a nudge would, nor merely tolerate one as a friction; it *harvests* it – and its design problem is the inverse of the usual one: not to add incentives, but to keep a single non-engineerable channel free of contamination by gain, reputation, and signalling – blindness as purification, removing informational channels until the only one left is the one that cannot be bought, faked, or gamed; the impossibility *is* the security property. The symmetric stake belongs to the same pattern: protection arises not

from strength deterring weakness but from shared, deliberate self-exposure – both parties post the same vulnerability, and it is exactly this symmetry that keeps the regime blind, the stake carrying no type information (§3). Whether other institutions can be built by such subtraction – removing information until only unpurchasable credibility remains – is a question beyond this paper.

Two readings must finally be separated: given a settled norm, the mechanism is *protection*, with reach and residual quantified above; absent one, it is the apparatus through which a norm could form at all ($N^* = R(N^*)$, §4.4). The paper establishes the first reading and formulates the second – the protective claim is conditional on the constituted regime, the constitutive claim a posed problem, not a resolved one.

7 Conclusion

A bilateral interaction between strangers can be protected against gain-motivated exploitation without compensating victims, building reputation, or verifying behavior: through a calibrated, destroying, self-costly button under a blind mechanism. The effect *is* deterrence – but with an unusual source of credibility, otherwise unavailable in the one-shot, anonymous case: not reputation or repetition, but the genuine, anticipated retaliatory disposition of the injured party; every engineered alternative either erodes the deterrence margin or merely reprises this disposition’s expression (Theorem 1). The quantity that governs everything is the self-cost ratio $\lambda = c/b$; its reciprocal $L = 1/\lambda$ is the punishment’s effectiveness. The limits are exact and stated above (§5): above all, credibility rests on the reality of the retaliatory disposition – empirically the best-documented piece –, on its harm-keyed activation – a posit, priced for failure –, and on its calibration, which we reduce to a stationary fixed point (Prop. 5) whose selection remains open, and in which, not in the reality of the disposition, the residual fragility sits. What remains is not a promise of safety but a credible threat whose reach and residual can be quantified – and, where no shared notion of the wrong yet holds, something narrower and larger at once: not a protection, but the one act by which such a notion could come to hold at all.

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